

Correlation potential of Wiener vis-a-vis Szeged indices : Anti-inflammatory activities of phenols

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Szeged index is a newly introduced index whose use in developing structure-activity-property relationships is yet to be established. The present paper deals with its application in developing quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR). The anti-inflammatory activity for a series of phenols is chosen for this purpose and the results are compared with those obtained from Wiener index.

It has been known for sometime that certain invariants of molecular graphs, usually referred to as topological indices, can be used to establish quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) of interest in pharmacology^{1,2}. The QSAR studies are certainly a major factor in contemporary drug design. Topological indices report translation of molecular structures into characteristic structural descriptor expressed as numerical indices which may then be used in QSAR studies. Thus, one-to-one correlation could be obtained between topological indices and activities of drugs. A plethora of topological indices for this purpose are reported in the literature¹⁻⁵. Among these topological indices, the Wiener index (W) is the first and widely used index⁴. A number of successful QSAR studies were made based on the Wiener index⁶.

Very recently, Gutman^{7,8} has introduced a new topological index named Szeged index and abbreviated as S_z . The applications of S_z index in QSAR studies are yet to be established. In view of the above, the present study was undertaken which deals with the modeling of anti-inflammatory activity of phenol derivatives (Table 1) using S_z . Another objective of the study was to compare the results obtained from S_z with those obtained using W . It may be noted that the modeling of anti-inflammatory activity of phenols by both W and S_z indices are not reported in the literature. Furthermore, as inflammation is a local physiological phenomenon, the transport of the anti-inflammatory agent to the target site from the point of application is important. As π reflects such pharmacokinetic phenomenon, study involving π would be more meaningful. Hence, the colinearity between π and $-\log IC_{50}$ was also investigated

Table 1 Wiener (W) and Szeged indices and π -values of phenols exhibiting anti-inflammatory activity

Compd no	R	HO-C ₆ H ₄ -R			π	$-\log IC_{50}$
		W	S_z	S_z/W		
1	H	64	109	1.7031	-	3.204
2	2-Me	86	144	2.1395	1.40	2.176
3	3-Me	88	146	1.6591	1.08	2.755
4	4-Me	90	152	1.6889	1.16	2.120
5	2-Br	86	144	2.1395	1.70	2.875
6	2,3-Me ₂	114	183	1.6053	2.12	1.806
7	2,4-Me ₂	116	189	1.6293	2.00	1.230
8	2,5-Me ₂	116	187	1.6127	1.92	1.653
9	2,6-Me ₂	112	181	1.6161	2.24	1.204
10	3,4-Me ₂	117	191	1.6325	1.68	1.806
11	3,5-Me ₂	116	189	1.6293	1.60	2.508
12	2,3,5-Me ₃	144	230	1.5972	1.92	1.431
13	2,3,6-Me ₃	144	226	1.5944	1.92	0.903
14	2,4,6-Me ₃	146	230	1.5753	2.00	0.845
15	2,3,5,6-Me ₄	180	275	1.5278	3.28	1.146

Anti-inflammatory agents are drugs used to counteract inflammation, a morbid process affecting some part of the body, characterized by excessive heat, swelling, pain and redness^{9,10}. The two most important classes of pharmacological agents that inhibit the acute or chronic inflammatory response are (i) the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and (ii) the adrenal glucocorticosteroid hormones or steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (SAIDs)¹⁰. Both SAIDs and NSAIDs interfere with the synthesis and release of prostaglandins (PG's) and of a large number of other mediators of inflammation derived from arachidonic acid¹⁰. Consequently, the need to design a new category of drugs that have lesser side-effects is enormous.

Several studies concerning the anti-inflammatory properties of phenols have appeared in literature¹¹⁻¹⁷. Like other anti-inflammatory agents, phenols inhibit prostaglandin and leukotriene synthesis and inhibit platelet aggregation. A large number of phenolic drugs have been used in the treatment of inflammation^{18,19}. Very recently, Ruiz *et al.*¹¹ have suggested that the ability of phenols to form phenoxyl radical and the stability of their derived radicals are important in the anti-inflammatory activity of phenols. They have also calculated the enthalpies of formation of ground state (ΔH_{GS}), transition (ΔH_{TS}), and radical (ΔH_{RS}) states along with activation enthalpy (ΔH_A) and correlated them with the anti-inflammatory activities of phenol derivatives. Significant correlations were found between these thermodynamic parameters and the anti-inflammatory activity¹¹. But, as stated earlier, till date no QSAR study based on Wiener (W) and Szeged (S_z) indices are reported in the literature.

Molecular modeling :

In view of the above two molecular modeling techniques, one based on the S_z and other based on the W index, for a group of fifteen phenols (Table 1) were considered. In addition, model based on π was also investigated for comparison. Transformation of chemical structure of these phenols into mathematical graphs makes it possible to express the chemical structure of a phenol by a single number. Such a number characterizing a molecular structure (or a corresponding molecular graph), as stated earlier, is called topological index³. Therefore, a topological index expresses topological information for a given chemical structure. A standard approach is to use the hydrogen-suppressed graphs, defined as the graphs corresponding to the bare molecular skeletons^{3,5}. The advantage of topological indices is that they may be used directly as simple numerical descriptors in QSAR studies⁵. These relationships are mathematical models that enable the prediction of activities from structural parameters.

In the present investigation, we studied phenol derivatives because they exhibit interesting anti-inflammatory activities which may eventually lead to useful applications. The anti-inflammatory activities were adopted from the earlier work^{11,21,22}.

Methodology :

In order to be able to present our findings, we first need to specify our notation and terminology, in particular, to define S_z and W . Let G be the usual, hydrogen atom-depleted graph representation of the phenols under consideration^{3,5}. Hence, G is a connected graph without directed and multiple edges and without loops. By $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ we denote the vertex and edge sets, respectively,

of G . If e is an edge of G , connecting the vertices u and v , then we write $e = uv$. The number of vertices of G is denoted by $|G|$.

The distance between the vertices of G is defined as usual^{8,20}: the distance $d(v, w|G)$ between two vertices v and w of G is equal to the length of a shortest path, connecting these vertices.

Definition of the Wiener index (W)^{4,21}: Let v_1, v_2, \dots, v_w be the vertices of graph G . Then $d(v_i, v_j|G)$ will represent the distance between the vertices v_i and v_j . Then the Wiener index is defined as^{4,5}

$$W(G) = W = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N d(v_i, v_j|G) \quad (1)$$

Definition of Szeged index (S_z)^{7,8}: Let $n_1(e|G)$ be the number of vertices of graph G lying closer to one end of e ; let $n_2(e|G)$ be the number of vertices of G lying closer to other end of e , then the Szeged index is defined as^{7,8}

$$S_z = S_z(G) = \sum n_1(e|G) n_2(e|G) \quad (2)$$

with the summation going over all edges of G . In cyclic compounds there are edges equidistant from both ends of edge e , such vertices by the definition of S_z are not taken into account.

Biological data and thermodynamics functions: The anti-inflammatory activity *in vitro* is expressed by $-\log IC_{50}$ adopted from the earlier work^{11,21,22}. The thermodynamic parameters (ΔH_{GS} , ΔH_{TS} , ΔH_{PR} , ΔH_A) were also adopted from the earlier study¹¹.

Results and Discussion

Phenols (1-15), their π -values, Wiener (W) and Szeged (S_z) indices are given in Table 1. The ratio S_z/W is also presented in Table 1. Anti-inflammatory activities ($-\log IC_{50}$) as well as the thermodynamic parameters for the set of phenols used in the present study are recorded in Table 2. The regression parameters and the quality of correlations for the correlations of the activities and the thermodynamic parameters with W as well as S_z indices are given in Table 3. The estimated values for $-\log IC_{50}$ are shown in Table 4; the observed activity is also shown here for comparison.

A perusal of Table 1 shows that the values of both W and S_z indices increase with the increase in size of the substituent in the parent phenol moiety. Also that degeneracy is observed both in the values of W and S_z . This is obvious because according to Balaban²³, these indices belong to first generation topological indices wherein degeneracy is common. Table 1 also shows that for the set of phenols the ratio (S_z/W) is nearly constant (1.6695).

Table 2. Anti-inflammatory activity ($-\log IC_{50}$), enthalpies of formation of ground state (ΔH_{GS}), transition state (ΔH_{TS}), phenoxyradical (ΔH_{PR}) and activation (ΔH_A) of phenols

WHPO net	$-\log IC_{50}$	ΔH_{GS} kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH_{TS} kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH_{PR} kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH_A kcal mol ⁻¹
1	3.204	22.54	54.82	4.72	77.06
2	2.176	29.016	46.44	3.58	75.45
3	2.785	29.45	48.95	3.11	78.90
4	2.120	29.79	47.42	3.95	77.21
5	2.875	14.756	62.68	11.35	77.43
6	1.806	35.79	39.40	10.71	76.19
7	1.230	36.52	37.95	12.14	74.47
8	1.653	36.61	38.65	11.45	74.16
9	1.204	36.11	38.76	11.72	74.87
10	1.806	36.74	39.01	11.03	75.74
11	2.508	37.37	45.14	10.96	82.51
12	1.43	43.35	31.48	18.53	74.83
13	0.903	42.85	32.26	18.84	76.11
14	0.845	43.59	31.94	20.17	75.53
15	1.146	48.99	23.85	25.53	72.83

Table 3. Regression parameters for the correlation of S_z with W and the correlation of the activity/properties of phenol derivatives used in the present study (Table 2) with W and S_z

Compd.	Correlation	A	B	sd	γ
1	S_z-W	21.1486	1.4303	42.8210	0.9989
2	$-\log IC_{50}-W$	4.1840	-0.0204	0.7500	-0.8120
3	$-\log IC_{50}-S_z$	4.4997	-0.0143	0.7500	-0.8174
4	$-\log IC_{50}-\pi$	3.1223	-0.7665	0.5345	-0.5925
5	$\Delta H_{GS}-W$	4.2915	0.2669	8.7942	0.9075
6	$\Delta H_{GS}-S_z$	0.2692	0.1870	8.7942	0.9106
7	$\Delta H_{TS}-W$	75.9146	-0.3025	9.9314	-0.9108
8	$\Delta H_{TS}-S_z$	80.3413	-0.2112	9.9314	-0.9108
9	$\Delta H_{PR}-W$	-11.8930	0.2072	6.6078	0.9377
10	$\Delta H_{PR}-S_z$	-14.7553	0.1438	6.6078	0.9317
11	ΔH_A-W	81.8664	-0.0468	2.7440	-0.5178
12	ΔH_A-S_z	80.5568	-0.0234	2.2631	-0.4435

*A and B are correlation parameters, sd = standard deviation, γ = correlation coefficient.

Table 4. Estimated (Est.) and experimental (Expt.) anti-inflammatory activities of phenols and their residues*

Compd. no.	$-\log IC_{50}$ (Expt.)	$-\log IC_{50}$ estimated from			
		W		S_z	
		Est.	Residue	Est.	Residue
1	3.204	2.878	0.326	2.941	0.263
2	2.176	2.430	-0.254	2.441	-0.765
3	2.785	2.389	0.396	2.412	0.373
4	2.120	2.348	-0.228	2.326	-0.206
5	2.875	2.430	0.445	2.441	0.434
6	1.806	1.858	-0.052	1.883	-0.077
7	1.230	1.818	-0.588	1.797	-0.567
8	1.653	1.818	-0.165	1.826	-0.173
9	1.204	1.899	-0.695	1.911	-0.707
10	1.806	1.797	0.009	1.768	0.038
11	2.508	1.818	0.690	1.797	0.711
12	1.431	1.246	0.185	1.211	0.220
13	0.903	1.246	-0.343	1.268	-0.365
14	0.845	1.206	-0.361	1.211	-0.366
15	1.146	0.512	0.634	0.567	0.579

*Residue = difference between observed and estimated activity of phenols.

Therefore, for the chemically relevant members of the phenol derivatives used, we have as a good approximation,

$$S_z = \gamma W \quad (3)$$

where the multiplier γ (Table 1) has a value close to 1.6695. In other words, the S_z and W indices for the phenols used are linearly proportional. Thus, both the indices will have similar correlation potential in modeling properties and activities of phenol derivatives used in the present study. Eqn. (3) is the first relation established between the S_z and W indices of phenols used. Thus, at least in the case studied here, the content of information from S_z and W indices are essentially the same.

In order to confirm the aforementioned finding we have analyzed the inter-correlation of S_z with W using regression analysis. The regression parameters and quality of the correlation of S_z with W (Table 3) indicate that the correlation is outstanding ($R = 0.9989$). Therefore, using W and S_z indices for modeling and estimating anti-inflammatory activities of phenols as well as of estimating their thermodynamic properties, similar results will be obtained.

A perusal of Table 1 indicates that the activities of phenol derivatives based on $-\log IC_{50}$ follow the order :

$$1 > 5 > 3 > 11 > 2 > 4 > 6 = \\ 10 > 8 > 12 > 7 > 9 > 15 > 13 > 14 \quad (4)$$

Based on the substitution R, the above order of activity of phenol derivatives corresponds to the following substitution (R) sequence :

$$H > 2\text{-Br} > 3\text{-Me} > 3,5\text{-Me}_2 > 2\text{-Me} > 4\text{-Me} > \\ 2,3\text{-Me}_2 = 3,4\text{-Me}_2 > 2,5\text{-Me}_2 > 2,3,5\text{-Me}_3 > \\ 2,4\text{-Me}_2 > 2,6\text{-Me}_2 > 2,3,5,6\text{-Me}_4 > 2,3,6\text{-Me}_3 > 2,4,6\text{-Me}_3 \quad (5)$$

The above substitution sequence indicates that phenol has the highest $-\log IC_{50}$ value and that 2,4,6-trisubstituted phenol has the lowest one. Also that $-\log IC_{50}$ goes on decreasing with multi-substitution of methyl ($Me = CH_3$) group on the aromatic nucleus of phenol.

In terms of π -values of the substituent the following sequence is observed :

$$15 > 9 > 6 > 7 = 14 > 12 = 8 > 12 > 13 > 5 \\ > 11 > 10 > 2 > 4 > 3 > 1 \quad (6)$$

No quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) is observed in these cases.

In view of the above, we have correlated the anti-inflammatory activities of phenol derivatives with thermodynamic parameters, as well as with W and S_z indices. The correlations are then subjected to regression analysis using the method of least-squares. We observed that in all cases linear correlation is obtained. This colinearity is expressed by the following equation :

Activity or Thermodynamic property = $A + B TI$ (7)

where, A and B are the correlation parameters whose values for the respective correlations are given in Table 3. The qualities of these correlations as expressed by standard deviation (sd) and the correlation coefficient (γ) are also given in Table 3.

As seen from Tables 3 and 4, by means of eqn. (7), it is possible to quite accurately estimate the anti-inflammatory activities of phenols. The results (Table 4) have shown that these values are very close to the experimental ones. Thus, using the distance-based topological indices W and S_z , it is possible to infer about the pharmacological activities of these compounds. The results also show that both the topological indices have practically the same predictive ability, the Szeged index (S_z) being slightly better than the Wiener index (W).

It is worth-mentioning that the Szeged index is interesting for the cyclic graph. The graphs (phenolic derivatives) chosen here, however, consist of one and the same cycle. Also that, substituents and their positions were chosen systematically. They all are monocyclic graphs of ring size six carrying zero, one, two, or more tree like attachments.

It may be recalled that the graphs chosen (phenol derivatives) differ in the acyclic part only. Therefore, any variance of S_z depending on the structure in this study is caused by the acyclic parts, for which the correlation between W and S_z is trivial^{15,16}. Thus, the information derived from W and S_z differs only in degree, not in kind. That is why we found degeneracy in W and S_z and an outstanding correlation ($R = 0.9984$) between W and S_z thus exhibiting similar predictive ability. However, slightly better results obtained using S_z is due to its definition and due to the presence of cyclic structure on the phenolic derivatives.

Earlier²⁴, while discussing the property of S_z , we observed that three different types of information are obtained when the results obtained from S_z are compared with those obtained from W . These three categories are : (i) cases where W gives better results than S_z , (ii) cases where S_z gives better results than W , and (iii) cases wherein similar results are obtained using both W and S_z . The present study falls under category (ii).

At this stage, it is worth recording that inflammation is body's response to injury characterized by pain, heat, swelling, and redness. Pain is a receptor-mediated phenomenon, whereas swelling is due to gushing of body fluid, accumulation of histamine in the site in question. One of the reasons of redness is due to rush of blood to the spot. Hence, the phenomenon of inflammation is a complex process comprising of all these. In a complex drug action mechanism, the ultimate expression of biological (or physiological) activity is a function of steric, electronic,

and hydrophobic parameter of bioactive molecules. Furthermore, inflammation is a local physiological phenomenon. Hence, the transport of the anti-inflammatory agent to the target site from the point of application is important.

Thus, our results show that out of the aforementioned aspects, one of the aspects of the molecule (viz. the shape and size) is taken care of by W and S_z indices, and a linear regression model is used for this purpose. However, W or S_z alone cannot reflect totally the anti-inflammatory phenomenon.

The results (Table 4) obtained from π -values reflect pharmacokinetic phenomenon (i.e. transport of drug to the target site). The QSAR models based on the thermodynamic parameters together with the results obtained by using π -values, finally reflect drug action mechanism as well as the pharmacokinetic phenomenon. The results show that the drug activity mechanism and pharmacokinetics are controlled by ΔH_{GS} , ΔH_{TS} , ΔH_{RS} , ΔH_A . A perusal of Table 3 shows that the colinearity of W and S_z with ΔH_{GS} , ΔH_{TS} and ΔH_{PR} is outstanding. That is, the information obtained from grounded state-, transition state- and radical state-enthalpies as well as from W and S_z are similar. However, correlations of W and S_z with ΔH_A is not statistically significant. That is, activation enthalpy cannot be modeled by either by W or S_z .

Conclusion : From the above results and discussion, the following conclusions can be made. (i) Colinearity between Szeged index (S_z) and Wiener index (W) of the phenols is outstanding; therefore, they have similar ability in proposing QSAR/QSPR models. (ii) Degeneracy is observed in both the topological indices as they belong to first generation topological indices according to Balaban²². (iii) According to Balaban²², in spite of the observed degeneracy, the first generation topological indices are quite successful in QSPR as well as QSAR; the same is found to be true in the present case also. (iv) The correlation of anti-inflammatory activities of phenols and the thermodynamic parameters for the formation of phenoxy radical (ΔH_{GS} , ΔH_{TS} and ΔH_{PR}) with both W and S_z is also found outstanding. (v) The topological indices, W and S_z can be used successfully for estimating, modeling and predicting anti-inflammatory activities of phenols as well as they can be used for the estimation and prediction of the thermodynamic properties for the formation of phenoxy radical. (vi) Both W and S_z have similar predicting abilities for anti-inflammatory properties of phenol derivatives; however, S_z is found to be slightly better than W .

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